

ADVANTAGES AND CHALLENGES OF SUCCESSFUL IMPLEMENTATION OF ERP SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

In current years there has been enhancement in exercising on Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) systems in big concerns and government firms mostly in urbanized nations, whereas extensive acceptance of ERP systems in developing nations lags far away. It has been observed that there are many instances where ERP systems prove to be a failure either in the design or its implementation. A number of reasons contribute in the success or failure of an ERP systems.

Success or failure of the system depends upon the initial stage of adoption and implementation of the system.

Consideration of all issues and challenges at the initial stage may furnish a sound base for a successful ERP system implementation in an organisation. There is a significant need for considering ERP system implementation issues and challenges in developing nations, as ERP systems are still in their premature stages in these nations. Literature review on successful ERP system implementation disclose that there are many studies whispered by researchers, but very few have listed the success issues and challenges of ERP system implementation focusing on developing countries. Issues and challenges of ERP system implementation in developing nations differ from those of developed nations. The main objective of this study is to unearth the issues and challenges of successful ERP system implementation in developing nations like India. Data are collected by having an extensive literature review of about past fifteen years. Analysis and synthesis of collected data reveals that clear scope of implementation, top management commitment, proper implementation strategy, proper vendor selection, project management, user training & education, end user involvement and lack of experienced implementers are the important issues and challenges. Understanding of issues and challenges will help organizations to adopt appropriate implementation strategies leading to success of ERP system in an organization.

Keywords: ERP, Company, Solution, Advantages

INTRODUCTION

ERP is an integrated set of software modules linked to a common database, handling basic corporate functions. It attempts to integrate all departments and functions across a company into a single computer system that serves different departments particular needs such as planning, manufacturing, accounting, distribution, sales, human resource, inventory management, service and maintenance, transportation and e-business. ERP can be viewed as a software solution that

addresses the enterprise needs taking the process view of the organization, to meet the organizational goals tightly integrating all functions of an enterprise.

Enterprise resource planning systems, also called enterprise systems (ES) are among the most important business information technologies that emerged during the last decade. While no two industries' ERP systems are the same, the basic concept of ERP systems is focused on standardization and synchronization of information, and as a result, improved efficiency.

ERP systems differ qualitatively from prior large scale Information Technology (IT) implementations in three ways :

- 1) ERP impacts the whole organization,
- 2) Employees may be learning new business processes in addition to new software, and
- 3) ERP is often a business led initiative, rather than IT led.

In the context of ERP project implementation, challenges represent major pitfalls which, if not addressed, may cause the failure of a project.

Therefore, it is important to understand the real-life implementations, problems and related scenarios in detail.

LITERATURE REVIEW

ERP implementation issues are necessary to encourage. Therefore, various aspects of ERP implementation have attracted the attention of academicians, researchers and policymakers from time to time in the country. The literature reviews are: ERP implementations usually involve broad organizational transformation processes, with significant implications on the organization's management model, structure, management style and culture, and particularly, on people [Caldas & Wood, 1999]. AMR research Inc., the leading industry and market analysis organization specializing in enterprise enabling technologies, predicts that the enterprise resource planning (ERP) software market will grow at a compound annual growth rate of 37 % over the next five years [Caruso 1998].

This market will continue to be one of the largest, fastest growing, and most influential in the applications industry, and is poised for steady growth into the new millennium, says AMR. Before ERP came into existence, different departments had their own software system to meet their requirements. This resulted in a fragmentation of information, as all of the information was stored separately on different systems in business units, factories etc. sometimes spread across the world.

This made it impossible to get accurate information on time. In 1990s, globalization led to immense competition and companies, especially in the manufacturing sector, realized the need for more customer focus and shortened product life cycles. Corporations had to move towards agile manufacturing, continuous improvement of business processes and business process reengineering.

This required an integration of manufacturing with other functional areas like accounting, marketing, HR, etc. This led to the evolution of MRPII to ERP systems (Sadagopan, 1999). ERP combines all the business functions together into one single integrated system with a single central database. This system serves the information needs of all the departments across geographies, while allowing them to communicate with each other. As illustrated in fig-1, a typical ERP system consists of modules for manufacturing, Production Planning, Quality Management, Financial Management, Human Resource, Manufacturing and Logistics and Sales and Distribution.

Once an enterprise wide implementation is in place, operating managers are relieved of routine decisions and they thus have the time to plan and execute long-term decisions that are vital for the growth of an organization. It leads to significant cost savings as the health of the organization is continuously being monitored. Though the cost of an ERP system is very high, it becomes insignificant in the face of the benefits a proper ERP implementation provides in the long run (Sadagopan, 1999). Nowadays, the ERP industry is one of the most promising ones, which contrasts with the obvious lack of related academics research. In case of small and medium scale industries (SMI) of India the study revealed that for ensuring successful ERP implementation the six major factors on clarity in goals and objectives behind the implementation, adequacy of user training, competency of the project implementation team, acceptance of changes brought about by the implementation and adequate vendor support and external consultant participation had a key role to play. (Parijat Upadhyay, 2008) Similar studies conducted in china by creating interactive structural model have identified four critical factors on the funds support, department's participation; training and service of the supplier of ERP which influence s the system of ERP implementation most directly.

The four factors above are critical factors which decide the ERP system is successful or not (Ranzhe Jing et al, 2007). According to Huin unless the differences between SME and large companies are clearly conceived, the ERP project will not reach to positive outcome (Huin, S.F. 2004,) We believe that organizations and vendors should play an important role in researching on ERPs, because this kind of research is amenable to be field-based rather than laboratory-based. Consultants also play an important role in the research of some issues; over the years, they have accumulated probably the richest ERP experiences through thousands of ERP installations worldwide. The best practices for ERP implementation in SMEs are investigated by using a problem driven approach by dividing implementation process into several components which will reflect the nature of ERP projects and makes them distinctive from other systems design. Methods critical issues relating to developing entrepreneurship for sustainable development of

SMEs for its future extensions and added benefits are also addressed (Rashmi Jha et al, 2004). Effective communication is critical to ERP implementation (Falkowski et al., 1998). Expectations at every level need to be communicated.

Management of communication, education and expectations are critical throughout the organization (Wee, 2000).

OBJECTIVES:

- i. To determine the advantages and challenges of ERP system implementation
- ii. To suggest remedial measures for better utilization of ERP

RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

ISSUES AND CHALLENGES

Though the market for ERP seems to be growing, there are several issues and challenges one has to contend with when implementing an ERP system in the SME segment. Some of these are:

Awareness: There is a low level of awareness amongst SMEs for ERP vendors, applications etc. most of the time they do not even know what ERP systems are and what they can do. They consider ERP systems to be a magic wand, which will help solve all their business problems, be it in terms of quality, or process defects. ERP brings in a more disciplined execution of business process giving more transparency and visibility to the working of the organization.

Perception: SMEs have the perception that ERP is meant only for large firms mainly owing to the high costs of acquisition, implementation and maintenance as also the complexity. Some of the SMEs even feel they do not need ERP.

Earlier Implementations: SMEs have heard of the much-publicized failures in ERP implementation, which have led firms to bankruptcy. Some SMEs who have implemented ERP earlier have failed.

This has led SMEs to believe that ERP implementations are a waste of time and effort and can even lead to the demise of company.

Approach to implementation: ERP vendors advise SMEs to mould the business to ERP's way of working. Considering that ERP systems will bring it best business practices. This is the plain vanilla approach that was mentioned earlier, which would bring down the cost of implementation. But most. SMEs have processes that they have evolved over time and hold very

dear to their hearts. As a result, SMEs are having the entire ERP system customized to meet their requirements. This would increase the overall cost of implementation. A good approach would be to keep the customization to a minimum.

Cost: SMEs have less of capital than their larger counterparts.

Change management: One of the major reasons why ERP implementations nationwide have been known to fail is due to the implementation being considered as an automation project instead of one that involves change management. This results in the system being put in place but not being used effectively due to people not ready to accept the change.

Limited resources: Most SMEs do not have an in-house IT team. Due to this they have to rely on external agencies to help them and this adds to the implementation costs.

BENEFITS OF ERP SYSTEMS APPLICATION

Implementing an ERP class system is a very big business challenge. The basis for the smooth implementation of ERP systems is: the employees' engagement and the modern approach of the management, quickly getting acquainted with the software and appropriately using it in day-to-day work. The biggest obstacle against the ERP use, however, is financial, especially among small and medium-sized enterprises. Nevertheless, more and more entrepreneurs are beginning to implement the ERP systems because they see numerous benefits of their application 6,7: [9-11]

- Shortening the time necessary to reach the recipient,
- Better order management,
- Cost reduction,
- Customer service improvement,
- Information integration between the company's departments,
- Improving the efficiency of procurement processes,
- Distribution or production processes improvement,
- Economic and financial situation improvement,
- Enhanced staff skills,
- Increased data security,
- Automation and unification of data,

- Current access to information,
- Increase in goodwill.

CONCLUSIONS

The commitment of top management has been recognized as one of the most important elements in the successful implementation of ERP system. Since the primary responsibility of top management is to provide sufficient financial support and adequate resources for building a successful system, Implementing an ERP package is a complex and costly undertaking, so it's essential to choose the appropriate vendor, adequate scalability features, suitability of H/W and user friendliness of product depending on the size and structure of an organization Project management related factors like Clear goal and objective, Effective project management, Reasonable expectation, Other dept. participation, Change request, Implementation strategy, Data conversion, Clear & effective communication are very critical for a successful ERP implementation. Team member should understand the inner workings of their respective departments thoroughly. And the team must have can do attitude It is not enough to implement simple software, but a multi-module ERP system. These systems are mainly used in large and medium-sized Polish companies, which stems primarily from the size of their needs but also the high cost incurred during the implementation and operation of the system. Micro and small businesses often cannot afford to implement them for financial reasons.

It should be emphasized that ERP systems are an example of complex software, the implementation of which is often a difficult challenge for an enterprise. An enterprise using the ERP system is dependent on the system, so it is necessary to adjust it properly, at the stage of the system implementation, to the needs of the company.

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